

On the Alleged Acceleration of Taurocholate Hemolysis by Normal Serum.

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In a previous paper on the mechanism of hemolysis (Sen and Basu, *This Journal*, 1928, 5, 1) one of us has shown that the permeability of the membrane of the red blood corpuscles is determined by the colloidal condition of the membrane. The view has also been put forward that the hemolysis by saponin, bile salts or by soaps is due to the peptisation of some of the membrane constituents such as lecithin or cholesterol, and it was shown both from our experiments as well as from those of others that normal serum inhibits this hemolysis. So far as this inhibiting action of normal serum is concerned, an interesting fact has been observed by Ponder (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1923, B 95, 403) several years ago, namely that inhibition is obtained if serum protein is first added to the red cells and then the hemolyte is added, but when the serum is added to a mixture of red cells and hemolyte, an acceleration of hemolysis is observed. This has only been observed in the case of taurocholate hemolysis, but not in the case of saponin hemolysis. This acceleration of taurocholate hemolysis was not explained by Ponder on the basis of current theories, and appears to be quite surprising. Since some emphasis has been put on this phenomenon in a recent article (*Nature*, 1927, 120, 304) and as no further experiments seem to have been published by Ponder on this acceleration of hemolysis by normal serum, it was thought desirable to make some experiments in this line and curiously enough, we have got quite different results. Owing to the importance of the results of Ponder on theoretical grounds, we quote them below to show their nature.

TABLE I.

Taurocholate Hemolysis.

	Time of hemolysis.
1 in 3,000 taurocholate	3'5 minutes
1 in 3,000 taurocholate, plus 0'025 c.c. serum, added before the addition of red cells...	32 ..
1 in 3,000 taurocholate, plus 0'025 c.c. serum, added 1/2 minute after the addition of cells	0'6 ..

TABLE II.
Saponin Hemolysis.

	Time of hemolysis.
1 in 30,000 saponin	3-25 minutes
1 in 30,000 saponin <i>plus</i> 0.025 c.c. serum added before the addition of red cells	37 "
1 in 30,000 saponin <i>plus</i> 0.025 c.c. serum added 1/2 minute after the addition of cells	37 "

It will be apparent from these tables that in the case of taurocholate there is an acceleration of hemolysis if the serum is added to the mixture of the hemolyte and the red cells. As we have not been able to corroborate this, some of our results will be given.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Ponder in his experiments used human erythrocytes in normal saline. In our experiments we have used mainly sheep's corpuscles both in saline as well as in isotonic sucrose. Some data with human corpuscles are also given later on. Defibrinated blood corpuscles were washed repeatedly with isotonic saline or sucrose as the case may be, and then suspended in it to give a concentration of 1 per cent. All the solutions as well as the glass apparatus used in this investigation were sterilised before use. The method of determining complete hemolysis was by means of a visual comparison with a standard fully hemolysed tube of the same concentration. Where percentage hemolysis has been given, these were also found by a similar method. For comparative purposes, the method was quite good. The hemolytes were dissolved in the proper solutions.

The results are given in the following tables. The experiments given in Tables III to V were all done in isotonic sucrose. The original taurocholate concentration was 5 per cent., total volume 5 c.c., and the temperature 22°. In the second column is given the time in minutes for complete hemolysis.

TABLE III.

	Time of hemolysis.
1. 2 C.c. red cells <i>plus</i> 1 c.c. taurocholate	12
2. 2 C.c. red cells <i>plus</i> 0.05 c.c. serum <i>plus</i> 1 c.c. taurocholate	49
3. 2 C.c. red cells <i>plus</i> 0.1 c.c. serum <i>plus</i> 1 c.c. taurocholate	59
4. 2 C.c. red cells <i>plus</i> 1 c.c. taurocholate <i>plus</i> 0.05 c.c. serum added 1 minute after the addition of the taurocholate	26½
5. 2 C.c. red cells <i>plus</i> 1 c.c. taurocholate <i>plus</i> 0.1 c.c. serum added 1 minute after the addition of the taurocholate	35

TABLE IV.

	Time of hemolysis. (minutes)
1. 1.5 C.c. red cells plus 0.5 c.c. taurocholate	5
2. 1.5 C.c. cells plus 0.05 c.c. serum plus 0.5 c.c. taurocholate ...	20
3. 1.5 C.c. cells plus 0.1 c.c. serum plus 0.5 c.c. taurocholate ...	70
4. 1.5 C.c. cells plus 0.5 c.c. taurocholate plus 0.05 c.c. serum added 2 minutes after the addition of the taurocholate	7½
5. 1.5 C.c. cells plus 0.5 c.c. taurocholate plus 0.1 c.c. serum added 2 minutes after the addition of taurocholate	18

TABLE V.

1. 1 C.c. red cells plus 0.5 c.c. taurocholate	3
2. 1 C.c. cells plus 0.5 c.c. serum plus 0.5 c.c. taurocholate ...	10
3. 1 C.c. cells plus 0.1 c.c. serum plus 0.5 c.c. taurocholate ...	35
4. 1 C.c. cells plus 0.5 c.c. taurocholate plus 0.05 c.c. serum added 3 minutes after the addition of taurocholate	3
5. 1 C.c. cells plus 0.5 c.c. taurocholate plus 0.1 c.c. serum added 3 minutes after taurocholate addition	3

So long these experiments were made in sucrose solutions. As Ponder's experiments have been carried in saline, similar experiments were also carried out by us. In the following tables, taurocholate is 1 per cent., total volume 5 c.c., and the corpuscle concentration is 1 per cent. All preparations were made in physiological saline.

TABLE VI.

	Time of hemolysis.
1. 2 C.c. red cells plus 1 c.c. taurocholate	10 mins.
2. 2 C.c. cells plus 0.05 c.c. serum plus 1 c.c. taurocholate ...	240 mins.
3. 2 C.c. cells plus 0.1 c.c. serum plus 1 c.c. taurocholate ...	No hemolysis in 240 minutes.
4. 2 C.c. cells plus 1 c.c. taurocholate plus 0.05 c.c. serum added 1 minute after the addition of the taurocholate	135 mins.
5. 2 C.c. cells plus 1 c.c. taurocholate plus 0.1 c.c. serum added 1 minute after the addition of the taurocholate	About 60% hemolysis in 240 minutes.

TABLE VII.

	Time of hemolysis.
1. 2 C.c. cells plus 1.5 c.c. taurocholate	8 mins.
2. 2 C.c. cells plus 0.05 c.c. serum plus 1.5 c.c. taurocholate ...	About 20% hemolysis in 135 mins.
3. 2 C.c. cells plus 0.1 c.c. serum plus 1.5 c.c. taurocholate ...	No hemolysis in 150 mins.
4. 2 C.c. cells plus 1.5 c.c. taurocholate plus 0.05 c.c. serum added $\frac{1}{2}$ minute after the addition of the taurocholate ...	85 % hemolysis in 135 mins.
5. 2 C.c. cells plus 1.5 c.c. taurocholate plus 0.1 c.c. serum added $\frac{1}{2}$ minute after the addition of the taurocholate ...	35 % hemolysis in 150 mins.

TABLE VIII.

1. 2 C.c. cells plus 2 c.c. taurocholate	5 $\frac{1}{2}$ mins.
2. 2 C.c. cells plus 0.05 c.c. serum plus 2 c.c. taurocholate ...	150 mins.
3. 2 C.c. cells plus 0.1 c.c. serum plus 2 c.c. taurocholate ..	No hemolysis in 150 mins.
4. 2 C.c. cells plus 2 c.c. taurocholate plus 0.05 c.c. serum added 1 minute after the addition of the taurocholate ...	150 mins.
5. 2 C.c. cells plus 2 c.c. taurocholate plus 0.1 c.c. serum added 1 minute after the addition of the taurocholate ...	45% hemolysis in 150 minutes.

Several more tables of this nature were obtained but these are not given here. All these experiments were made with taurocholate as the hemolyte. It should be noted that in sucrose solutions more of taurocholate is necessary to hemolyse the same amount of the corpuscles than in saline solutions. Evidently sucrose has an inhibiting action on taurocholate hemolysis. Ponder has shown that in saponin hemolysis, no peculiar behaviour is observed with serum. It was therefore thought desirable to investigate the effect of serum on oleate hemolysis, and Table IX gives the results. The solutions were made in isotonic sucrose. The potassium oleate concentration was 0.025 per cent. and the total volume of the mixture 5 c.c.

TABLE IX.

	Time of hemolysis.
1. 2 C.c. red cells plus 0.2 c.c. oleate ...	20 $\frac{1}{2}$ mins.
2. 2 C.c. cells plus 0.05 c.c. serum plus 0.2 c.c. oleate ...	80% hemolysis in 60 minutes.
3. 2 C.c. cells plus 0.1 c.c. serum plus 0.2 c.c. oleate ...	Slight hemolysis only in 60 minutes.
4. 2 C.c. cells plus 0.2 c.c. oleate plus 0.05 c.c. serum added 1 minute after the addition of the oleate ..	36 minutes.
5. 2 C.c. cells plus 0.2 c.c. oleate plus 0.1 c.c. serum added 1 minute after the addition of the oleate. ...	60 minutes.

So long all the results were obtained with sheep's corpuscles. Since Ponder's work has been mainly done with human erythrocytes, some data of this nature have also been obtained by us. The blood used was obtained from one of the authors, and the corpuscles were defibrinated and washed with saline. The total volume of the mixture was 5 c.c., final concentrations of corpuscles and taurocholate were 0.4 per cent. and 0.06 per cent. respectively, and the temperature 26°. The figures indicate the time for complete hemolysis. All solutions were made in physiological saline.

TABLE X.

		Time of hemolysis.		
(1)	Corpuscles + taurocholate	8½ mins.
(2)	Corpuscles + taurocholate + 0.01 c.c. serum added one minute after the addition of the taurocholate	15 mins.
(3)	Corpuscles + taurocholate + 0.02 c.c. serum added one minute after taurocholate	25 mins.
(4)	Corpuscles + taurocholate + 0.03 c.c. serum added one minute after taurocholate	80 mins.

Discussion.

The results given in the foregoing tables will show conclusively that in no case there is an acceleration of hemolysis due to the addition of normal serum, but in every case there is a retardation. It should be stated here however that while making hemolytic experiments with low amounts of corpuscles, in one or two cases an actual acceleration was found to take place, but these results could not be reproduced. It is very difficult to obtain a sharp end point with small amount of corpuscles. This is undoubtedly due to the liberation of hemoglobin which has been shown by Ponder to have a retarding effect on hemolysis. Owing to this fact the time for complete hemolysis may not be exact, but as in each table the results are quite comparative, the conclusion we have arrived at is experimentally true. For this reason, we think that Ponder's results (compare also *Proc. Roy Soc.*, 1927, B 101, 212) may be due to some particular conditions affecting his experiments and are not true as general cases.

In view of our experimental results, the theoretical difficulty of explaining the action of serum on hemolysis disappears, and the

facts can be made to agree with existing theories. Whatever may be the real explanation of the reaction between the corpuscle surface and the hemolyte, we consider that the effect of serum is one of competition for the erythrocyte surface, because a similar assumption has been found useful in sedimentation and agglutination experiments. P. L. du Nouy ("Surface Equilibria of Biological and Organic Colloids," 1929) has shown that normal serum when examined immediately has a higher surface tension than pure water, and thus has an antagonistic action towards hemolytes like soap, bile salts or saponin which tend to lower the surface tension of water. In the previous pages we have shown that this antagonistic action finds an easy explanation from a purely colloidal point of view. Whether that explanation is right or wrong is another matter, but so far as the present experiments are concerned, they can be explained without assuming any particular difference between taurocholate hemolysis and saponin hemolysis. All that our results show is that the time necessary for complete hemolysis is less when the serum is added to the red cells after the addition of the hemolyte than the time required when it is added before the addition of the hemolyte. This is quite natural, because in the first case, the hemolyte being alone in contact with the surface of the erythrocyte, has been adsorbed to a greater extent and the disintegrating influence of the adsorbed hemolyte has already proceeded to a certain extent. The effect of serum is consequently less marked than in the case where serum is added previous to the addition of the hemolyte. Consequently we believe that there is no essential difference in the mechanism of the hemolytic action of soaps, bile salts or saponin. Our experimental results given in this paper, if corroborated, will show, contrary to Ponder's implied suggestions, that the effect of serum in the inhibition of hemolysis is the same in every case, and that a single view will explain the hemolytic behaviour of saponin, soap or bile salts.

Finally one remark may be made regarding the mechanism of this inhibition by serum about which we have said nothing so long. There is a prevalent view that serum proteins combine with the hemolyte thus making it ineffective. In a recent paper in this *Journal* (Sen and Basu, *loc. cit.*) we have suggested that the serum proteins may have a sensitising effect on some of the colloidal constituents of the cell membrane whereas the bile salts have a peptising effect on them.

Hence the antagonism between these two substances is really an antagonism between a sensitising agent and a peptising agent in diphasic system. From the work of D'Herelle ("Immunity in Natural Infectious Diseases," English Edition, 1924) it seems that the hemolysis by immune sera or that by heterologous sera is very likely due to coagulating action on the membrane constituents. This coagulating action depends upon the particular physico-chemical state of the proteins in the immunised sera and not due to the presence of any new body as was supposed in the previous paper. Consequently normal serum may be assumed to have at least a sensitising effect on the stroma. But from a further study of the effect of normal serum on the erythrocyte surface, specially in sedimentation and agglutination experiments which have been made by us, it appears that this effect does not seem to be a complete explanation of the inhibition observed. It is concluded that apart from this type of antagonism, there is a tendency of the serum proteins to be adsorbed on the surface of some of the membrane constituents, and this adsorption is strong enough to displace the adsorption of the hemolyte from the surface of the stroma. An effect of this nature is evident in the case of some agglutination experiments by heavy metal salts. On this view we can picture the whole process as follows:—The action of the hemolytes is on the stroma, and hemolysis by substances which diminish the surface tension of solutions such as bile salts, saponin or soaps is due to a peptisation of some of the membrane constituents like lecithin or cholesterol. This peptisation is preceded by an adsorption of these hemolytes by the surface. An inhibition of this type of hemolysis can be caused either by sensitising the peptisable constituents so as to make them less easily peptisable or by inhibiting or displacing this adsorption of the hemolyte by the addition of another strongly adsorbable substance. The effect of normal serum appears to be due to both these causes so far as hemolytes of the class of bile salts are concerned. It is doubtful if the serum proteins chemically combine with the hemolytes of this class to produce the so-called non-hemolytic bodies.

Summary.

- (1) Sucrose appears to have an inhibiting effect on taurocholate hemolysis of sheep's red blood corpuscles.
- (2) Normal serum has been found to inhibit the hemolysis of sheep's erythrocytes by sodium taurocholate both in sucrose as well as

in saline, and by oleate in sucrose. No accelerating influence of serum has been observed in the case of taurocholate hemolysis, and Ponder's results in this line have not been corroborated.

(3) The view has been put forward that the hemolysis of red-blood corpuscles by saponin, soaps or bile salts is due to a peptising influence of these substances on some of the membrane constituents, and that there is no essential difference in the mechanism of hemolysis by saponin, soaps or bile salts. The action of normal serum is also of the same nature in presence of all these peptising hemolytes.

(4) The effect of normal serum on hemolysis appears to be two-fold. Firstly, owing to a sensitising action on some of the membrane constituents it makes them less easily peptisable, and secondly, owing to its great adsorption on the surface of the stroma, it displaces the adsorbed hemolyte from the cell surface. When present before the addition of the hemolyte, it may hinder the adsorption of the hemolyte to any extent depending on its concentration. Simply the sensitising influence of the normal serum is not a sufficient explanation of the observed antagonism between serum and hemolyte, as was assumed to be the case in the previous paper.

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